

INTELHEART MULTIDISCIPLINARY SYSTEM FOR IMPROVED DIAGNOSIS OF HEART FAILURE

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Heart failure (HF) is a global health challenge, impacting over 64 million people worldwide [1], having severe prognosis and substantial socioeconomic impact. This paper aims to highlight how innovative Decision Support Systems (DSS) and computational platforms like INTELHEART [2] can revolutionize healthcare and facilitate early diagnosis of HF. The core concept involves integrating patient-specific data such as demographic and physical characteristics, medical history, symptoms, and diagnostic findings into a cloud-based environment. This data will be processed using advanced tools in the artificial intelligence (AI) and computational modeling, enabling creation of a virtual patient population. AI-driven systems can identify early indicators of HF by analyzing a patient's comprehensive clinical profile, including laboratory results, medical imaging, and electronic health records. Additionally, voice characteristics will be collected as biomarkers from participating patients to develop the VoiceHeart mobile app. By analyzing vocal biomarkers associated with HF, healthcare providers can detect the condition earlier, potentially before noticeable symptoms emerge. Recent studies indicate that subtle changes in a patient's voice may reflect underlying physiological changes linked to cardiovascular conditions, including HF [3].

INTELHEART represents a groundbreaking step forward in HF care by leveraging AI-driven analytics, a robust DSS, a cloud-based platform, and the VoiceHeart app to support both clinicians and patients. Furthermore, it incorporates assessments of psychological resilience and emotional well-being, addressing critical but often-neglected mental health aspects crucial to comprehensive HF management.

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